

13th INTERNATIONAL
CONGRESS
OF THE SERBIAN SOCIETY
OF TOXICOLOGY

1st TOXSEE
REGIONAL
CONFERENCE

Present and Future of toxicology: Challenges and opportunities

10 - 12 May, 2023 Belgrade

electronic

ABSTRACT
BOOK

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DEAR COLLEAGUES, DEAR FRIENDS,

We are delighted to greet you on the **13th International Congress of the Serbian Society of Toxicology & 1. TOXSEE Regional Conference - Present and Future of toxicology: challenges and opportunities**, organized in Belgrade from 10-12 May 2023.

Five years after our last international Congress we gathered in Belgrade, to further promote contemporary toxicology, in the broadest sense of meaning, as a response to the new challenges requiring innovative approaches and solutions, as it is understood in the third decade of the XXI century.

Initial concept, to blend the top scientific level in toxicology with the potentials of its' use in broad array of clinical and other domains, proved to be right. Line-up of more than 70 first class international and regional faculties as well as best Serbian scientists and toxicology professionals in all related domains fully justify the approach. Moreover, interest and presence of more than 250 colleagues from Serbia and region witness that our professional community has recognized the approach taken and shown vast interest.

The Serbian Society of Toxicology is committed to innovation and creativity in research and education, in cooperation with collegial associations and institutions in Serbia and abroad. As a regional leader, we developed and inaugurated the regional brand TOXSEE, with the idea to gather as much as possible expertise and know-how from the region and Europe, to capture knowledge, share experience and exchange practical skills with colleagues who deal with toxicology problems daily.

Time imposes on us the need to integrate science, top knowledge and daily practice in a quality and efficient way, to contribute to the better health of the society as a whole in the most purposeful manner. Therefore, a thematic and functional connections with domains of emergency medicine, general medicine, paediatrics, ecology, in addition to already standard toxicological disciplines i.e. clinical, forensic, occupational, and experimental toxicology have been enhanced.

We are glad to host you in a pleasant atmosphere of Belgrade in mid-May, to benefit from the attractive and dynamic program, exchange knowledge, and, equally important, to refresh existing and establish new contacts with colleagues and friends, while enjoying our hospitality and cherish the moment in one of the best partying cities of Europe.

YOU ARE MOST WELCOME!!!

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- President of the 13th STC Congress

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IZLOŽENOST NIKLU KAO ZAGAĐIVAČU ŽIVOTNE SREDINE KOD PACIJENATA IZ VOJVODINE SA ADENOKARCINOMOM PLUĆA

ENDOCRINE
DISRUPTORS

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Međunarodna agencija za istraživanje raka klasifikovala je jedinjenja nikla (Ni) kao Grupu 1 kancerogena za ljude, dok je metalni nikl u Grupu 2B, verovatno kancerogen za ljude. Jedinjenja nikla se koriste u proizvodnji nerđajućeg čelika i drugih legura nikla, katalizatora, baterija, pigmenata i keramike. Pošto je nikl veoma rasprostranjen industrijski zagađivač, opšta populacija je izložena niklu kroz kontaminirani vazduh, zemljište, hranu i vodu za piće. Izloženost prašini nikla iz rafinerije i prašini sup-sulfida nikla prepoznata je kao faktor rizika za razvoj karcinoma pluća. Cilj ovog rada bio je odrediti izloženost niklu među muškim pacijentima sa uznapredovalim adenokarcinomom pluća. U ovom istraživanju prve jutarnje uzorke urina dalo je 36 pacijenata muškog pola (39-84 godine) sa inoperabilnim IIIB i IV stadijumom adenokarcinoma pluća, dijagnostikovanih na Institutu za plućne bolesti Vojvodine, Srbija. Nikl je određen ICP-MS u uzorcima. U 69,44% (25/36) uzoraka urina Ni je detektovan iznad granice kvantifikacije. Izmereni nivoi nikla bili su iznad referentnih nivoa u urinu od 1-3 µg/L za zdrave odrasle osobe koje je definisao ToxGuide Američke agencije za toksične supstance i registar bolesti. Koncentracije nikla u urinu kod posmatranih pacijenata bile su čak 446,50 µg/L. Iako je glavni neželjeni efekat izloženosti niklu kontaktni dermatitis, nijedan od pacijenata izloženih Ni nije prijavio kontaktni dermatitis. Skoro 70% pacijenata sa adenokarcinomom pluća (sa neoperabilnim IIIB i IV stadijumom) iz Vojvodine je izloženo niklu iznad nivoa za zdrave odrasle osobe.

KLJUČNE REČI: zagađenje, adenokarcinom pluća, epidemiološka studija, nikl endokrini ometač

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EXPOSURE TO NICKEL AS ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTANT AMONG LUNG ADENOCARCINOMA PATIENTS IN VOJVODINA

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The International Agency for Research on Cancer has classified nickel (Ni) compounds as Group 1 carcinogenic to humans while metallic nickel as Group 2B, possibly carcinogenic to humans. Nickel compounds are used in the production of stainless steel and other nickel alloys, catalysts, batteries, pigments, and ceramics. Since nickel is widespread used industrial pollutant, the general population is exposed to nickel through contaminated air, soil, food and drinking water. Exposure to nickel refinery dusts and nickel subsulfide was reported as risk factor for lung cancer.

The aim of this study was to determine the exposure to nickel among advanced lung adenocarcinoma male patients. In this research 36 male patients (39-84 years old) with inoperable IIIB and IV stadium of lung adenocarcinoma, diagnosed in the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina, Serbia provided their first morning urine samples. Nickel was determined by ICP-MS in the samples. In 69.44% (25/36) urine samples Ni was detected above the limit of quantification. In all analysed samples the nickel levels were above urinary reference levels 1-3 µg/L for healthy adults defined by the ToxGuide of the US Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry. The nickel urinary concentrations in the observed patients were up to 446.50 µg/L. Although the main adverse health effect of nickel exposure is contact dermatitis, none of the Ni exposed patients reported contact dermatitis. Almost 70% of lung adenocarcinoma patients (with inoperable IIIIB and IV stadium) from Vojvodina are exposed to nickel above levels for healthy adults.

KEYWORDS: pollution, lung adenocarcinoma, epidemiological study, nickel, endocrine disruptor

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